

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**EVALUATION OF BIOSYNTHETIC PATHWAYS AND METABOLIC
ENGINEERING OF MICROBES FOR TERPENOID PRODUCTION-
REVIEW ARTICLE****Mehr un Nisa¹, Madiha Saleem¹, Mehmood Khan¹, Fouzia Karam Khan¹, Robina Manzoor¹,
Kaleem Imdad, Bilquees Fatima², and Aamir Rasool¹**¹ Institute of Bio-Chemistry, University of Balochistan, Quetta Pakistan.² Department of Zoology University of Balochistan Quetta Pakistan.**Abstract:**

The main focus of this review is the production of terpenoid from metabolic engineering of microbes and different biosynthetic pathways are also explained briefly. Natural production of Terpenoid from plants is in a low concentration, and can be used in medicines as antibacterial agent. Production of terpenoid by the recombination of microbes give high concentration of terpenoid that's why in this review the metabolic engineering of microbes for the production of terpenoid is discussed. A collective policy of metabolic engineering is to raise the endogenous resource of precursor metabolites to advance pathway efficiency. The capability to additional increase heterologous manufacture of a preferred complex might be restricted by the innate capability of the smuggled pathway to quarter great precursor resource. Metabolic engineering is the permitting equipment for the administration of live lyexistence to construction high-value facilities of alike natural and heterologous derivation. In the case of heterologous construction, well-characterized microbes are recycled as construction hosts for targeted optimization can be achieved using approximately accessible inherited tackles also artificial biology structures. One significant presentation of engineered microscopic organisms is geared in the direction of the production of terpenoid natural yields. Terpenoids characterize the largest classes of secondary metabolites that contains medicines, greasepaints (cosmetics), and appro aching biofuels aspirants. Terpenoid is belongs to the class of isoprenoids that extracted from plants. Isoprenoids are naturally occurring in various structurally range. Terpenoid is the extraction of plants that can be used in different material for fragrance, used as medicine against bacteria.. Terpenoids speak to the biggest group of characteristic products. Their basic assorted variety is fundamentally because of the variable spine created by terpene synthase. Terpenoid can be overproduced in microbes as researchers work on it. Different biosynthetic pathways such as MEP and isopropine pathway take place for biosynthesis of terpenoid. Bioactive aquatic organisms, bio fuels, microbes and other natural products are highly in use for the terpenoid production. E coli play a vital role in production of terpenoid, which is increasing the interest of researchers towards E. coli. Furthermore terpenoid production is possible from fungi and plats as well. Terpenoid produced in industries at high level Metabolic engineering policies to yield terpenoids in microscopic orders such as E. coli as well mold have largely engaged on accumulative the precursor flux into the heterologous terpenoid pathway by transmitting endogenous isoprenoid metabolism. These production schemes have trust eddeplyon exchanging the enzyme attentionsnow the creation passageway.

Key words: (RuBisCO), Ribulose-1.5-bisphosphate carboxylase.(IDP), Isopentenyl diphodphste. (DMADP), Dimethylallyl diphosphate.(6-MSAS), 6-methylsalicylic acid synthase.(MEP), mevalonate pathway.(MVA) non mevalonate pathway.

Corresponding author:

Mehr un Nisa,
Institute of Bio-Chemistry,
University of Balochistan,
Quetta Pakistan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Mehr un Nisa et al., *Evaluation of Biosynthetic Pathways and Metabolic Engineering of Microbes for Terpenoid Production- Review Articles*., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(11).

INTRODUCTION:

Metabolic engineering is a technique in which cellular and metabolic characteristics of host organism is use to produce desirable products at high productivity. This technique changes the organism's metabolic pathway to obtain the meaningful end product. Production of secondary metabolites can be improved by metabolic engineering. Metabolic engineering of microbes is being done for the production of terpenoid as well. Terpenoid is a class of isoprenoids that extracted from plants. Isoprenoids are naturally occur in various structurally range the concentration of terpenoid in plants is generally very low. So mostly alternative methods are used to extract terpenoids for drugs for example, artemisinin, for engineering *Escherichia Coli* through mevalonate pathway for over production of terpenoid. (Vincent JJ Martin 2003). The group of unicellular prototroph naturally produce armature for production of recombinant protein. Phototrophic non sulfur purple alpha proteobacteria are capable to crop in sunbeams and as well fasten the atmospheric CO₂ and dinitrogen. Therefore, for the analysis of actions as well as parameter of photosynthesis these microorganisms besides unicellular organisms are extremely worn as representation organisms. The ribulose-1.5-bisphosphate carboxylase (RuBisCO) moreover nitrogenase in addition to hydrogenase enzyme composite. An entire metabolic pathway allows the shift at the same time as well as functional appearance of particular gene as different appearance apparatus. Terpenoids has been engineered through different approaches. (Vincent J J Martin et al). Terpenoids have prevalent functions and it belongs to biggest family of naturally occurring products. Metabolic engineering and discovery of natural products is biggest challenge of overproduction of terpenoids and well organized field of new terpenoids. Overproduction of the terpenoids in microbial system, in labotary the recreation tactics emphasize on coherent engineering and targeted engineering gives additional information. The development of formation new terpenoids enhances and strong precursor provides optimized. Terpenoids for the efficiency of host and it provide platform speedy panel for terpene cyclases (GuangkaiBian). The entire terpenes are derivates of C₅ constructed from (IDP) isopentenyl diphosphste and (DMADP) dimethylallyl diphosphate. From two distinct pathways they are formed, (MEP) pathway and (MVA) pathway. MEP pathway is present in unicellular organisms such as bacteria and in plastids of plant cell. MVA pathway also present in various microbes and cytosol of fungus, animals and plants (Smit et al., 2000; Degenhardt et al., 2009;

Nagegowda, 2010; Lombard et al., 2011).

Terpene synthase has dual distinctive metabolic pathways, a mevalonate-subordinate pathway situated in the cytosol as well as projected to wards remain connected through the production of sesquiterpene (C₁₅), and a substrate providing by dual varied metabolic pathways. It is in responsibility of the synthesis of plentiful terpenes in plants. (C₅), mono- (C₁₀) and diterpene (C₂₀). The stuffs of abilities plus protein involved through substrate and ended outcome biosynthesis and in accumulation activities in metabolic engineering have revealed the occurrence of numerous substrate terpene synthases. (Pazouki & Niinemets, 2016). The improvement of terpene cyclization existed significant for the transformative allowance of invention diverse modification however stops ambiguous show ever. The main exposure of an epistatic scheme of credits governing the start of terpene cyclization in *Artemisia annua*. The terpene synthase start form amorpha-4. 11-diene synthase (ADS) and (E)-b- Farnesene synthase (BFS) and distribution cyclic terpenes or direct terpenes, exclusively. (Salmon et al, 2015). Artificial biology propose fresh potential use for the overproduction of compound natural goods via optimizing additional theoretically willing microbial hosts. (Alper HS et al, 2007. Ajikumar PK, et al. 2008).

Metabolic engineering of microbes for terpenoid production

Metabolic engineering and some of current development in the synthetic natural sciences suggest many possibilities for higher production of major composite native foodstuffs. from the engineering of microbes biosynthetic pathways suggested many possibilities for the high production of major composite native food stuffs with the help of metabolic engineering and some of current development in the synthetic natural sciences. The mission includes,

1. The appearance of various far off, bulky and multidomain enzymes to cause difficulties.
2. In the novel host the accretion of poisonous far-off metabolites.

With the help of this mission it rebuilds the large biosynthetic pathways by production of natural foodstuffs molecular technology into microbial hosts. From the newly resources bio-fuels and bio chemical production in microbial cell factory and engineering of bioactive molecules.

Ajikumar Parayil Gregory 2009) Metabolic

Engineering for the Production of Natural Products
In the field of medical health care the innate foodstuffs and their derived take part in an essential function in the treatment of much savior infection and as stimulation for chemically manufacture therapeutics. Through recombinant DNA technology as well as move ahead sequencing. Metabolic engineering is a progressively more dominant technique to advance accepted produce titers and produce narrative compound. Most of the pathways of biosynthetic are dependable in the production of pharmaceutically precious compounds and chemically complex have been elucidated. (Lauren B)

Heterologous formation platform contain enable admittance to pathway as of not easy to culture strain, metabolic as well as biological modeling instrument contain a resulted into growing systematic as well as critical potential progress in appearance method moreover instruction contain facilitate the modification of pathways used for improved effectiveness, as well as categorization of personality pathway machinery have support the manufacture of fusion passageway on behalf of the construction of new composite. These come first in the numerous characteristic of metabolic engineering contain not just succumb attractive systematic innovation other than as well construct it an gradually more practical advance on behalf of the optimization of ordinary creation biosynthesis. Natural products produces from bacteria, fungi and plants are well-off resource of bioactive complex used for remedy invention along with advance. Natural yield conquered in the early hours drug discovery while great showing series be locate up subsequent the get through segregation in addition to therapeutic appliance of penicillin in the 1940s (Li JWH, Vederas JC. 2009) 1990 this ratio of drugs use were natural products and their inspired (Harvey AL 2008). Inside additional current years this number have reduce in kindness of artificial multiple libraries though ordinary goods motionless take part in an essential function in drug innovation. On or later than the period 1981–2006, 52% of the original substance creature standard via the FDA be expected goods otherwise natural product encouraged (Newman DJ, Cragg GM 2007).

Ordinary goods are as well phrase secondary metabolites, or else person's not compulsory used on behalf of enlargement of the produce organisms. different primary metabolites necessary used for enlargement and be generally the similar diagonally band of living wage, secondary metabolites be able to vary extensively starting variety to variety in addition

to include a varied assortment of composite substance organization. Several of these multiple are structurally composite, containing several chiral centers as well as labile connectivity, which build them solid to manufacture chemically. Biosynthesis and fermentative move toward are as a result significant tackle in the making and growth of this complex for pharmaceutical, agricultural. (Demain AL, Adrio JL 2008). Metabolic engineering are set up for the balanced vary in the hereditary structure of a creature to modify the metabolic sketch otherwise recover biosynthesis potential (. Stephanopoulos G, Nielsen J 1998)

Genetic engineering of microorganism for the production of terpenoid flavor and fragrance compounds.

Aroma industries have highly interested in terpenoid flavor and fragrance compounds. They produced terpenoid by utilizing microbes as they can provide production of terpenoid at low cost and renewable resources by genetically engineering. The central C5 prenyl diphosphates act as a precursor, and convert into final product. (Florence M. Schempp, et al. 2017).

Metabolic engineering of fungi for terpenoid production

Rising significance in natural yield obtained from fungus is suitable to the role of fungi, 30% of which contributes in microbial innate products. Polyketides are main class of fungal natural products, which is consist of compounds, NRPs and Beta-lactams, terpenoid with their combination, are made up of peptide (Watanabe K 2003). Most of these applicable in medical field such as drugs of cholesterol lower (lovastatin) which produce the set of PKSs, renowned beta-lactams penicillin, cephalosporin along with the cyclic peptide immunosuppressant cyclosporine. For secondary metabolites fungi is good source because they grow in lower carbon resource also have upgrading in stain improvement which ensuing in strategy consequential in multi-gram for every liter give way of the yield of pharmaceutical (Watanabe K 2002) for appearance of fungal genetic material cluster is the mRNA dispensation with the aim of might be necessary to produce well-designed protein.

This make heterologous fungal strains a gorgeous selection as single be able to sidestep the point in time overshadowing mission of remove introns as well as edging genes through PCR to facilitate is necessary toward make sure right appearance in *E. coli* and yeast (Lubertozzi D, 2009). Similar to the actinomycetes, some of the further strong, fine

characterize fungal strains have well candidate used for heterologous hosts meant for genetic material cluster which initiate from further disobedient strain. Earliest example of a metabolite formed via a fungal synthase into a heterologous host is 6-methylsalicylic acid, which is synthesized via the multifunctional PKS 6-methylsalicylic acid synthase (6-MSAS). Doing well heterologous phrase be achieve in *S. coelicolor* CH999 (Bedford DJ.), *E. coli* (Kealey JT, 1998), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Kealey JT (1998) and *Aspergillus nidulans* (Fujii I 1996). Inside all except the fungal host, the introns be detached starting the gene encoding 6-MSAS. exclusive of a few additional optimization, yield as of bacteria be approximately 60–75 mg/L (Bedford DJ, Kealey JT,1998), whereas creation into *A. nidulans* be over 300 mg/L (Fujii I 1996) and yeast formed 1.7 g/L (Kealey JT,1998). Further up to date example in *E. coli* and fungal hosts contain the heterologous creation of beauvericin in *E. coli* (Xu Y 2008) and rebuilding of the four genetic material corridor to construct tenellin in *Aspergillus oryzae* (Heneghan MN 2010). Heterologous hosts contain as well be worn to fast fungal synthases on behalf of in vitro revise. The extremely falling iterative PKS LovB beginning the lovastatin pathway was newly spoken in addition to purify on or after an engineered *S. cerevisiae* strain (Ma SM 2009). Though heterologous appearance of fungal metabolites is at rest in the improvement phase, these success display with the aim of heterologous hosts be a workable selection used for the overproduction of fungal metabolites. (Schümann J, 2006, Schneider P 2008).

Metabolic engineering of bacteria for the production of terpene

Natural antibiotic produced by microbes and bacteria is responsible for 70% of producing of antibiotics.

The bacterial genus *Streptomyces* produces by actinomycetes over 70% (Berdy J 2005) the biggest group of naturally occurring bacteria they produce the natural products are as following,

Polyketides (tetracycline & erythromycin)

Non-ribosomal peptides NRPs (vancomycin & daptomycin)

Hybrid polyketide NRP antibiotics (epothilone)

Beta- lactams (cephamycin)

Several bacterial strains are good established and good characterized for the genetic modification methods still it concerned as a slow bacteria as compare to other bacteria's (Hopwood DA 2000)

Role of the MEP pathway in biosynthesis of isoprene and their precursors

The recognition of the enzymes as well as intermediates of the MEP pathway, it be experimental so as to the pathway not just provide to isoprenoid biosynthesis, Fig. (1). in addition the utilize of DXP (3) used for thiamine and pyridoxol construction, it have newly been revealed that HMBPP (8) be capable of worn while a precursor used for the biosynthesis of the plant hormones cytokinins in *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* (Krall L 2002) and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Takei K, Dekishima Y 2003). A current work by means of brand intermediates of the MVA or the MEP pathway in *Arabidopsis* sapling have established to facilitate the MEP pathway manufacture the precursor meant for the production of cytokinins such as trans-zeatin and isopentenyladenine derived, while a huge portion of the prenyl cluster of cis-zeatin derivatives is supply by the MVA pathway (Kasahara H, 2004). In mycobacteria, nucleotide conjugates of HMBPP come out to take action while phosphoantigens (natural nonpeptide-phosphorylated ligands) mixed up in the creation of V-delta-9/Vgamma- 2 T lymphocytes [Belmant C, 2009]. Fresh work has obviously recognized that HMBPP itself is an effective and definite activator for these cells (Eberl M, Hintz M 2003). The establishment and oligoclonal extension of V-delta-9/V-gamma-2 T cells (which are limited to humans and superior primates) are sensible past disease with a wide variety of pathogenic bacteria (such as *Brucella*, *Campylobacter*, *E.coli*, *Listeria*, *Mycobacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, *Salmonella*, and *Yersinia*) and protozoa (including *Plasmodium*, *Toxoplasma*, and *Leishmania*), except is not pragmatic with bacteria missing the MEP pathway (such as *Streptococcus* and *Staphylococcus*). Even though the task of these cells in protection is immobile not completely unstated, their establishment be measured central for the parameter of the protected comeback in disease like tuberculosis and malaria. The inspection that HMBPP is the main inducer of V-delta-9/V-gamma-2 T-cell reactivity towards lots of pathogenic bacteria and protozoa might have chief implication used for the growth of chemotherapeutics, immunotherapeutic as well as vaccines not in favor of a few of the majority detrimental catching disease (,Eberl M. , Hintz M 2003). The taking part of HMBPP or/and other intermediates of the MEP pathway in other task in addition isoprenoid manufacture remnants to be recognized.

Figure 2: In this figure the MEP pathway are shown enzymes are in bold and the genes are in italics and specifically inhibited step are also shown such as FR900098 and fosmidomycin.

Terpenes, Their Precursors and Its Synthesis

Each and every terpenes are derivative as of C5 structurewedges, (IDP) and (DMADP). They formed resources of dualdispersedpaths, the mevalonate pathway, which efficiency in archaea as well as in a rare bacteria as well as into the cytosol of plant life, wild life and mildews, along with 2-C-methyl-D-erythritol-4-phosphate (MEP) pathway here a large amount microbes and within herbal plastids plus joined organelles i.e. Apicomplexa of apicoplasts (Smit et al, 2000; Degenhardt et al., 2009; Nagegowda, 2010; Lombard et al, 2011).

In flora anchorage two mainly self-governing pathways meant for construction of terpene originator, MVA and MEP pathways, current job has open edupan stimulating narrative along with subsequently distant secreted feature of instruction of terpene production so as to confront the existing consent on the compartmentalization and instruction

of terpene production. In exacting, there was proof that more than little TPSs are multi-substrate. TPSs to facilitate be able to utilize pre nyldiphosphates among dissimilar sequence measurement lengthwise before dissimilar cis/trans arrangement as substrates. Enzymes, competent of manufacture terpenes of assorted sequence distance end to end relianttaking place consequent substrate accessibility (Pazouki et al., 2015). Surrounded by multi-substrate enzymes, a few be able to appearance monoterpenes through GDP while the substrate plus sesquiterpenes through FDP like the substrate (Gutensohn. 2013).

Natural impact of the discovery of multi-substrate put on wonder as allowingtowards the recent consent, hemi terpene, monoterpene, and di terpene creations are restricted to plastids as well asdepend on substrates supply by means of the MEP pathway, although sesqui terpene synthesis restrained to cytosol in addition to depend on substrates present

through the MVA pathway (Figure1; Keeling et al., 2008).

In plants in cooperation pathways (MEP and MVA) manufacture the similar substrates, DMADP and IDP; here has be a venerable mystery the same as to whether the two pathways be able to swap over metabolites (Rodrigueze et al., 2002). A confident replace of IDP stuck among cytosolic as well as plastid separation have be careful while the mainly possible position of junction of the dual pathways (Schwender et al., 2001; Bicket al, 2003). even though the whole inter compartmental substitute of terpene substrates beginning one partition to pathway instability in the further vice- cellular slot is slight below non- worried situation, the import of cross-talk amongst the pathways capacity raise beneath pressure situation to facilitate mostly repress terpene creation

in single pathway or underneath definite developmental step (Rasulov et al., 2015). Moreover, substrate substitute by the side of superior isoprenoids' that as GDP have been too exposed to exist achievable (Dong et al., 2016). Actuality, some current information make obvious to monoterpenes is able to be manufactured by multi-substrate sesquiterpene synthases in the cytosol (Gutensohn et al., 2013). Such a multi-substrate utilize facility be capable of supply a substitute resources for instruction of mono- and sesquiterpene manufacture during variation of cytosolic band volume of unlike substrates. Restingtaking place the further offer in attendance is confirmation of sesquiterpene construction in plastids (Nagegowda, 2010). moreover, mitochondria mighttheoretically donate to together mono-and sesquiterpene synthesis (Figure2, Dong et al., 2016).

Figure: 3 Thick lines indicate the usual accepting of terpenoid synthesis compartment amongst cytosol and plastid (Tholl et al, 2011), shiny the situation that monoterpene and diterpene synthases anchorage a chloroplast-targeting peptide stay functionally energetic in plastids and sesquiterpene synthases absent the aim peptide are energetic in cytosol., terpenoid synthesis survive capable to as fine potentially get set in mitochondria (Dong et al., 2016). For instance, targeting linalool/(E)-nerolidol synthase (FaNES1) from *Fragaria ananassa* on behalf of protein particulars to the mitochondria run to the construction of (E)-neroli do land homo terpene 4,8-dimethylnona-1,3,7-triene (DMNT) in transgenic *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants (Kappers et al., 2005). DMADP, dimethylallyl diphosphate (C5); MEP pathway, 2-C-methyl-D-erythritol 4-phosphate/1-deoxy-D-xylulose 5-phosphate pathway; IDP, isopentenyl diphosphate (C5); FDP, farnesyl diphosphate (C15); GDP, geranyl diphosphate (C10); GGDP, geranylgeranyl diphosphate (C20); NDP, neryl diphosphate (C10).

A probable multi-substrate make consumption of trendy together plastids and cytosol release awake a before non-considered chance of variation of terpene manufactured goods side vision by alteration in band volume of substrates through dissimilar series distance end to end. This might be of exacting significance intended for fragrant flora that requires particular terpene storage space arrangement. Since no prolonged genetic material appearance is required, just transform in substrate band sizes might product in rapid modification of the little bunch in such genus. Within actuality, an ability of multi-substrate utilize be able to be additional extensive than at this time renowned, since so distant, practical classification of TPSs is frequently carry out through just a only substrate or partial series of substrates (Rajabi *et al.*, 2013).

Future expectation of metabolic engineering in the field of medical.

Metabolic engineering have many futures expect and challenges in the field of medical the main opportunity of metabolic engineering is for anticancer drug such as Taxol. Taxol is very excusive and demanding with many attractive biochemical features. The native organism competes the biosynthetic steps are consists of 19 enzymes, many challenges face to transfer the microbial host. Furthermore, construction in the inhabitant creature, as fine the similar since compound production is illiterate and unsalable used in favor of the invention of Taxol. Therefore manufacturing the biosynthesis of Taxol is a demanding choice toward speed up the enlargement of compound biosynthetic trail engineering in microorganisms used for great range sustainable construction of Taxol and equivalent terpenoid molecules. It has need of the propose of a microbial cellular atmosphere, accomplished of supply originator wanted for Taxol biosynthesis in addition to the practical reconstitution of the heterologous Taxol biosynthetic enzymes. metabolic engineering in addition to artificial biology tackle close to transform the upstream endogenous MEP in *E. coli* by way of downstream heterologous Taxol biosynthetic pathways, consequential in a strain skilled of overproducing near the beginning Taxol originator. Moreover, multivariate modular move toward the passageway engineering threadbare the instruction of the non-mevalonate isoprenoid pathway in bacteria. The current study has opened up the new possibilities high level microbial invention well-off in addition to different substance organization in terpenoid molecules. at the same time as engineered passageway be comprehensive to consist of extremely lengthy passageway, such as the

inclusive 19 enzyme Taxol passageway original cell engineering, passageway manufacturing as well as protein engineering, tackle motivation require in the direction of be residential to sturdily state the passageway in addition to manufacture the invention.

CONCLUSION:

Terpenoid has functional activities as plant hormones, in pigmentation, waxes. It can be used for communication and defense due to their physiological and structural appearance. Metabolic engineering is a technique in which cellular and metabolic characteristics of host organism is use to produce desirable products at high productivity. This technique changes the organism's metabolic pathway to obtain the meaningful end product. Production of secondary metabolites can be improved by metabolic engineering. Metabolic engineering of microbes is being done for the production of terpenoid as well. Terpenoid production from different microbes, bacteria, fungi, aquatic plants and natural products enhance the availability of terpenoid because terpenoid itself when produced it takes too much time but when produced in industries it will take less time to produce greater quantity. Main focus is on *E. coli* because it play vital role in production of terpenoid with high quantity. Terpenoid is being used as antiseptic agent and for flavor in different aroma industries.. Some bioactive aquatic organisms, bio fuels, microbes and other natural products are highly in use for the terpenoid production. *E. coli* play a vital role in production of terpenoid, which is increasing the interest of researchers towards *E. coli*. Furthermore terpenoid production is possible from fungi and plats as well. Terpenoid produced in industries at high level. Production and metabolic pathway of terpenoid from different organisms such as *E. coli* and plants is briefly explained in this paper.

REFERENCES:

1. Li JWH, Vederas JC. Drug discovery and natural products: end of an era or an endless frontier? *Science*. 2009;325:161–5
2. Harvey AL. Natural products in drug discovery. *Drug Discov Today*. 2008;13:894–901.
3. Newman DJ, Cragg GM. Natural products as sources of new drugs over the last 25 years. *J Nat Prod*. 2007;70:461–77
4. Demain AL, Adrio JL. Contributions of microorganisms to industrial biology. *MolBiotechnol*. 2008;38:41–55
5. Stephanopoulos G, Nielsen J, Aristidou A. *Metabolic Engineering*. San Diego: Academic Press; 1998.
6. Berdy J. Bioactive microbial metabolites. *J Antibiot*. 2005;58:1–2613. Hopwood DA, Kieser T, Bibb M, Buttner M, Chater K. *Practical Streptomyces Genetics*. Norwich: John Innes Foundation; 2000.
7. Watanabe K, Rude MA, Walsh CT, Khosla C.

- Engineered biosynthesis of an ansamycin polyketide precursor in *Escherichia coli*. *Proc Natl AcadSci USA*. 2003;100:9774–8
8. Watanabe K Biosynthesis and biotechnological production of statins by filamentous fungi and application of these cholesterol-lowering drugs. *ApplMicrobiolBiotechnol*. 2002;58:555–64.
 9. Lubertozzi D, Keasling JD. Developing *Aspergillus* as a host for heterologous expression. *Biotechnol v*. 2009;27:53–75
 10. Bedford DJ, Schweizer E, Hopwood DA, Khosla C. Expression of a functional fungal polyketide synthase in the bacterium *Streptomyces coelicolor* A3(2) *J Bacteriol*. 1995;177:4544–8
 11. Kealey JT, Liu L, Santi DV, Betlach MC, Barr PJ. Production of a polyketide natural product in nonpolyketide-producing prokaryotic and eukaryotic hosts. *Proc Natl AcadSci USA*. 1998;95:505–9
 12. Fujii I, Ono Y, Tada H, Gomi K, Ebizuka Y, et al. Cloning of the polyketide synthase gene atX from *Aspergillus terreus* and its identification as the 6-methylsalicylic acid synthase gene by heterologous expression. *Mol Gen Genet*. 1996;253:1–10
 13. Xu Y, Orozco R, Wijeratne EMK, Gunatilaka AAL, Stock SP, et al. Biosynthesis of the cyclooligomerdepsipeptidebeauvericin, a virulence factor of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana*. *Chem Biol*. 2008;15:898–907.
 14. Heneghan MN, Yakasai AA, Halo LM, Song Z, Bailey AM, et al. First heterologous reconstruction of a complete functional fungal biosynthetic multigene cluster. *ChemBioChem*. 2010;11:1508–12.
 15. Ma SM, Li JWH, Choi JW, Zhou H, Lee KKM, et al. Complete reconstitution of a highly reducing iterative polyketide synthase. *Science*. 2009;326:589–92
 16. Schümann J, Hertweck C. Advances in cloning, functional analysis and heterologous expression of fungal polyketide synthase genes. *J Biotechnol*. 2006;124:690–703.
 17. Schneider P, Misiek M, Hoffmeister D. In vivo and in vitro production options for fungal secondary metabolites. *Mol Pharmaceutics*. 2008;5:234–42.
 18. Huang Q, Roessner CA, Croteau R, Scott AI. Engineering *Escherichia coli* for the synthesis of taxadiene, a key intermediate in the biosynthesis of taxol. *Bioorg Med Chem*. 2001;9:2237–42.
 19. Engels B, Dahm P, Jennewein S. Metabolic engineering of taxadiene biosynthesis in yeast as a first step towards Taxol (Paclitaxel) production. *Metab Eng*. 2008;10:201–6.
 20. Martin VJJ, Pitera DJ, Withers ST, Newman JD, Keasling JD. Engineering a mevalonate pathway in *Escherichia coli* for production of terpenoids. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2003;21:796–802.
 21. Ro D-K, Paradise EM, Ouellet M, Fisher KJ, Newman KL, et al. Production of the antimalarial drug precursor artemisinic acid in engineered yeast. *Nature*. 2006;440:940–3.
 22. Minami H, Kim J-S, Ikezawa N, Takemura T, Katayama T, et al. Microbial production of plant benzylisoquinoline alkaloids. *Proc Natl AcadSci USA*. 2008;105:7393–8.
 23. Hawkins KM, Smolke CD. Production of benzylisoquinoline alkaloids in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Nat Chem Biol*. 2008;4:564–73.
 24. Horinouchi S. Combinatorial biosynthesis of plant medicinal polyketides by microorganisms. *Curr Opin Chem Biol*. 2009;13:197–204.
 25. Miyahisa I, Kaneko M, Funa N, Kawasaki H, Kojima H, et al. Efficient production of (2S)-flavanones by *Escherichia coli* containing an artificial biosynthetic gene cluster. *Appl Gen Mol Biotechnol*. 2007;68:498–504
 26. Gillam EMJ. Engineering cytochrome P450 enzymes. *Chem Res Toxicol*. 2008;21:220–31.
 27. Leonard E, Koffas MAG. Engineering of artificial plant cytochrome P450 enzymes for synthesis of isoflavones by *Escherichia coli*. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2007;73:7246–51.
 28. Chang MCY, Eachus RA, Trieu W, Ro D-K, Keasling JD. Engineering *Escherichia coli* for production of functionalized terpenoids using plant P450s. *Nat Chem Biol*. 2007;3:274–7.
 29. Shiba Y, Paradise EM, Kirby J, Ro D-K, Keasling JD. Engineering of the pyruvate dehydrogenase bypass in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for high-level production of isoprenoids. *Metab Eng*. Keasling
 30. JD. Gene-expression tools for the metabolic engineering of bacteria. *Trends Biotechnol*. 1999;17:452–60
 31. Leonard E, Ajikumar PK, Thayer K, Xiao W-H, Mo JD, et al. Combining metabolic and protein engineering of a terpenoid biosynthetic pathway for overproduction and selectivity control. *Proc Natl AcadSci USA*. 2010;107:13654–9.
 32. Chen Y, Smanski M, Shen B. Improvement of secondary metabolite production in *Streptomyces* by manipulating pathway regulation. *Appl Microbiol and Biotechnol*. 2010;86:19–25.
 33. Baltz RH. Daptomycin: mechanisms of action and resistance, and biosynthetic engineering. *Curr Opin Chem Biol*. 2009;13:144–51.
 34. Park SR, Han AR, Ban YH, Yoo YJ, Kim EJ, et al. Genetic engineering of macrolide biosynthesis: past advances, current state, and future prospects. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2010;85:1227–39.
 35. Peiru S, Menzella HG, Rodriguez E, Carney J, Gramajo H. Production of the potent antibacterial polyketide erythromycin C in *Escherichia coli*. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2005;71:2539–47
 36. Gruenewald S, Mootz HD, Stehmeier P, Stachelhaus T. In vivo production of artificial nonribosomal peptide products in the heterologous host *Escherichia coli*. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2004;70:3282–91
 37. Watanabe K, Hotta K, Praseuth AP, Koketsu K, Migita A, et al. Total biosynthesis of antitumor nonribosomal peptides in *Escherichia coli*. *Nat Chem Biol*. 2006;2:423–8
 38. Mutka SC, Carney JR, Liu Y, Kennedy J. Heterologous production of epothilone C and D in *Escherichia coli*. *Biochemistry*. 2006;45:1321–30
 39. Pfeifer BA, Wang CCC, Walsh CT, Khosla C. Biosynthesis of yersiniabactin, a complex polyketide-nonribosomal peptide, using *Escherichia coli* as a

- heterologous host. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 2003;69:6698–702
40. Baltz RH. *Streptomyces* and *Saccharopolyspora* hosts for heterologous expression of secondary metabolite gene clusters. *J IndMicrobiolBiotechnol.* 2010;37:759–72.
41. Boghigian BA, Pfeifer BA. Current status, strategies, and potential for the metabolic engineering of heterologous polyketides in *Escherichia coli*. *Biotechnol Lett.* 2008;30:1323–30.
42. Challis GL. Engineering *Escherichia coli* to produce nonribosomal peptide antibiotics. *Nat Chem Biol.* 2006;2:398–400.
43. Zhang H, Wang Y, Pfeifer BA. Bacterial hosts for natural product production. *Mol Pharmaceutics.* 2008;5:212–25.
44. Hoffmeister D, Keller NP. Natural products of filamentous fungi: enzymes, genes, and their regulation. *Nat Prod Rep.* 2007;24:393–416.
45. Eberl M, Jomaa H. A genetic basis for human gammadelta T-cell reactivity towards microbial pathogens. *Trends Immunol* 2003; 24: 407-9.
46. Eberl M, Hintz M, Reichenberg A, Kollas AK, Wiesner J, Jomaa H. Microbial isoprenoid . biosynthesis and human gammadelta T cell activation. *FEBS Lett* 2003; 544: 4-10.
47. Poquet Y, Constant P, Halary F, Peyrat MA, Gilleron M, Davodeau F, et al. A novel nucleotide-containing antigen for human blood gamma delta T lymphocytes. *Eur J Immunol* 1996; 26: 2344-9.
48. Belmant C, Espinosa E, Poupot R, Peyrat MA, Guiraud M, Poquet Y, et al. 3-Formyl-1-butyl pyrophosphate A novel mycobacterial metabolite-activating human gammadelta T cells. *J Biol Chem* 1999; 274: 32079-84.
49. Kasahara H, Takei K, Ueda N, Hishiyama S, Yamaya T, Kamiya Y, et al. Distinct isoprenoid origins of cis- and trans-zeatin biosyntheses in *Arabidopsis*. *J Biol Chem* 2004 (in press)
50. Krall L, Raschke M, Zenk MH, Baron C. The Tzs protein from *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* C58 produces zeatin riboside 5'- phosphate from 4-hydroxy-3-methyl-2-(E)-butenyl diphosphate and AMP. *FEBS Lett* 2002; 527: 315-8.
51. Takei K, Dekishima Y, Eguchi T, Yamaya T, Sakakibara H. A new method for enzymatic preparation of isopentenyladenine-type and trans-zeatin-type cytokinins with radioisotope- 124. Smit A, Mushegian A. 2000. Biosynthesis of isoprenoids via mevalonate in archaea: the lost pathway. *Genome Res.* 10:1468–84 labeling. *J Plant Res* 2003; 116: 259-63.
52. Wilding EI, Brown JR, Bryant AP, Chalker AF, Holmes DJ, et al. 2000. Identification, evolution, and essentiality of the mevalonate pathway for isopentenyl diphosphate biosynthesis in gram-positive cocci. *J. Bacteriol.* 182:4319–27
53. Weber APM, Link M, Bhattacharya D. 2006. Single, ancient origin of a plastid metabolite translocator family in *Plantae* from an endomembrane-derived ancestor. *Eukaryot. Cell* 5:609–12
54. Zhou Z, Gu J, Li YQ, Wang Y. 2012. Genome plasticity and systems evolution in *Streptomyces*. *BMCBioinforma.* 13:S8
55. van Wezel GP, McDowall KJ. 2011. The regulation of the secondary metabolism of *Streptomyces*: new links and experimental advances. *Nat. Prod. Rep.* 28:1311–33
56. Rohmer M, Knani M, Simonin P, Sutter B, Sahn H. 1993. Isoprenoid biosynthesis in bacteria: a novel pathway for the early steps leading to isopentenyl diphosphate. *Biochem. J.* 295:517–24
57. Proteau PJ. 1998. Biosynthesis of phytol in the cyanobacterium *Synechocystis* sp. UTEX 2470: utilization of the non-mevalonate pathway. *J. Nat. Prod.* 61:841–43
58. Kovacs WJ, Olivier LM, Krisans SK. 2002. Central role of peroxisomes in isoprenoid biosynthesis. *Prog. Lipid Res.* 41:369–91
59. Disch A, Rohmer M. 1998. On the absence of the glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate/pyruvate pathway for isoprenoid biosynthesis in fungi and yeasts. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 168:201–8
60. Disch A, Schwender J, Müller C, Lichtenthaler HK, Rohmer M. 1998. Distribution of the mevalonate and glyceraldehydes phosphate/pyruvate pathways for isoprenoid biosynthesis in unicellular algae and the cyanobacterium *Synechocystis* PCC 6714. *Biochem. J.* 333:381–88.